

'Solar Shrine' at Lachish

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The 'Solar Shrine' is a small cultic building located on the northeastern side of Lachish (Tell ed-Duweir), and ancient settlement site in the Shephelah region of Israel. The building belongs to Stratum I, the period of Persian and Hellenistic occupation at Lachish, but the exact date of the 'Solar Shrine' is debated; it was used into the Hellenistic period (specifically the first half of the second century BC), but its date of construction belong to some point in the fourth or maybe as early as the fifth century BC, the mid-late Persian period. The name 'Solar Shrine' was given by its first excavator due to its eastern facing orientation and the assumption that this indicated a solar-based cult, but such orientation is known from other cultic buildings in the region without such a cult, and no other such connections are evident from finds in the structure. The structure consists of: a large court taking up most of the eastern side of the structure, with a few small rooms along its eastern border; a low staircase leading from the court up to an antechamber surrounded by a few other rooms; and an inner sanctuary approach through a few stairs up from the antechamber. This inner sanctuary included two plastered drains. As well as these drains, the cultic nature of the structure is indicated by a group of incense altars found in one room, and an altar found on the steps leading up from the court. The latter altar has, on different sides, an image of a hand and a figure with upraised arms, as well as a Hebrew or Aramaic inscription. The inscription is incomplete and different readings have been offered, but it seems to begin with the word "frankincense of", followed by a name and patronym. Because of the nature of the evidence, it is unclear what cult or cults were practiced in the structure. It may have been used for the cult of the god YHWH, the deity of the kingdom of Judah, in which Lachish had been an important fortress town during the Iron Age (specifically the tenth to 6th centuries BC). Lachish of Stratum I seems to have been an important local center for the Persian administration in the former area of this kingdom, so it may relate to the cult of those within the Persian administration at the site. The evidence is, however, inconclusive.

Date Range: 450 BCE - 150 BCE

Region: Lachish

Region tags: Israel

The archaeological site of Lachish, Israel

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Politically patrimonial and kinship-based (i.e. tribal, though this label is somewhat simplistic), which was the typical mode of organization of polities in this region and time.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Quite possible by the local Persian administration, but unknown.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Other [specify]

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: Lachish does not seem to have been densely occupied during Stratum I.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Field doesn't know

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1

– Source 2

– Source 3

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Though the British excavation was a pre-war excavation with a less "scientific" design that modern excavations.

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range

Has this place been looted:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ A group of structures:

– No

Notes: N/A

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and

Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Notes: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is a supreme high god present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the structure was used for the worship of YHWH, then use.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The many incense altars found would likely relate to rituals performed by individuals or small groups.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Possibly, large scale rituals incorporating all those resident in Lachish in Stratum I, or even from the surrounding area took place. But this is impossible to say without further evidence.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The drains found in the floor of the inner sanctuary could have been used for animal sacrifices, but may have been also been used, or used in stead for, libation offerings.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Nothing that can clearly be identified as an "offering" was found, but it is likely that there were offerings that were organic, ie plant and animal matter, that are simply no longer preserved, as is common in the archaeology of cultic places in this region. Moreover, the drains found in the floor of the inner sanctuary could have been used for libation offerings along with (or rather than) for animal sacrifices.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most likely, given that the structure seems to have been in use for some time, but there are no specific archaeological indications or repairs and such.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:
– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:
Economic documents, records etc.
– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:
– Yes

Notes: The biblical book of Nehemiah (11:30) indicates that Lachish was resettled by Judahites during the Persian period, though it is unclear how this might relate to the 'Solar Shrine;.

↳ Are they oral:
– No

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:
– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It may have served the cultic needs of the whole of Lachish during the time it was in use, but this is not clear.

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some of the rooms of the structure may have been for this purpose, but it is not clear.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Presumably there would have been some sort of specialist present (i.e. a priest), but we lack specific information.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The site may have locally, unclear.

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There may have been Persia and Hellenistic administration of the local area taking place at the site in these periods.

Bibliography

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